

UALG OPEN DATA CENTRE (UALG-ODC): ADVANCES, CHALLENGES, AND SIGNS FROM THE COMMUNITY

Ossama Dhaoui^a, Nuno Bicho^b, Cristina Veiga-Pires^c, Emilia Pacheco^d, Isabel Rocheta^e, João Cascalheira^f, José Barateiro^g, Lara Ferreira^h, Maria João Cruzⁱ, Nelson Corvo^j

^{a-j} Universidade do Algarve: cienciaaberta@ualg.pt

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17815652>

2 7 - 2 8
November
2 0 2 5

PLANNING

PLANNING

INTRODUCTION

PORTUGAL

is strongly committed to

Open Science

The University of Algarve follows all these initiatives and has launched the UAlg Open Data Center (UAlg-ODC)

- Adoption of the National Open Science Policy (2016).
- Development of the National Programme for Open Science and Open Research Data (PNCADAI), Funded through the Portuguese Recovery and Resilience Plan (PRR) to boost collaboration, research quality, and societal impact.

PLANNING

PRESENTATION OF UAlg-ODC

a strategic milestone for the institutionalization and operationalization of open science practices at the University of Algarve (UAlg), promoting the sharing, reuse, and enhancement of scientific knowledge generated at the institution. Aligned with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and the objectives of the National Plan for Open Science (PNCADAI);

The creation of UAlg-ODC comes at a time of growing demand from national and international funding bodies for research data to be made available in an open and reusable format. At the same time, it responds to UAlg's institutional commitment to enhancing the transparency, reproducibility, and visibility of its scientific output in an increasingly interconnected and collaborative global environment.

UAlg-ODC OBJECTIVES

- ✓ **O1: Develop a sustainable and cross-cutting infrastructure for research data management.**
- ✓ **O2: Establish a comprehensive institutional approach to Open Science and research data management.**
- ✓ **O3: Adopt and implement an institutional policy on Open Science.**
- ✓ **O4: Build internal capacity and competencies in Open Science and research data management.**

- ✓ **O5: Strengthen national and international collaboration in data stewardship.**
- ✓ **O6: Promote and monitor the adoption of FAIR and open data practices across all research domains.**
- ✓ **O7: Engage internal stakeholders and external audiences through effective dissemination and outreach activities.**

PLANNING

TASKS ESTABLISHED

The project started
in January 2025

Several important outcomes have already been achieved

1. Establishing working group;
2. Hiring and training of data steward;
3. Developing a preliminary draft of the institutional policy (it was launched for public consultation on October 16th);
4. Planning to meet different key stakeholders across faculties and research units;
5. To better understand community practices and perceptions regarding research data management, a survey was launched among faculty, researchers, and students.

TASKS ESTABLISHED

TARGETED ACADEMIC COMMUNITY AT UALG

■ Professors ■ Researchers ■ Master students ■ PhD students

PARTICIPANTS AT THE ODC SURVEY

■ Professors ■ Researchers ■ Master students ■ PhD students

Participation Rate was LOW

- Limited awareness
- Fragmented practices
- Weak institutional culture of Open Science at UAlg.

TASKS ESTABLISHED

In order to raise this limited awareness, UAlg-ODC has integrated a series of training sessions during the International Open Access week with main goals of :

- ✓ Promoting **Open Science practices** that enhance transparency, collaboration, and reproducibility.
- ✓ Equipping researchers with **practical tools** (e.g., Zotero) for efficient literature management and data sharing.
- ✓ Ensuring **compliance with FCT's Open Access policy** and understanding of publishing options (hybrid, gold, diamond).
- ✓ Fostering a **culture of open data** through effective data organization and management planning.
- ✓ Strengthening researchers' ability to **assess the reliability and credibility** of scientific publications.
- ✓ Encouraging **responsible researcher evaluation** based on open and ethical research practices rather than traditional metrics.

Other training sessions are programmed to be in December related to data management and data repository.

20 OUT | SEG
Zotero, Gestor Bibliográfico de PDF's e literatura
Online | Comunidade académica
Inscrição: <https://tinyurl.com/3z9p3w>

21 OUT | TER
Open Science and Researcher Evaluation
Presencial - Biblioteca Gambelas | Docentes, investigadores e estudantes de mestrado e doutoramento
Inscrição: Membros da UAlg <https://tinyurl.com/3z9p3w>

22 OUT | QUA
Onde publicar com a nova política da FCT: revistas híbridas, GOA ou diamante
Online | Docentes, investigadores e estudantes de mestrado e doutoramento
Inscrição: Membros da UAlg <https://tinyurl.com/ydk32yc>
Externos: cienciaaberta@ualg.pt

23 OUT | QUI
Rumo a uma cultura de dados abertos: da organização à partilha apoiada no PGD
Online | Docentes, investigadores e estudantes de mestrado e doutoramento
Inscrição: Membros da UAlg <https://tinyurl.com/3amu7n2b>
Externos: cienciaaberta@ualg.pt

24 OUT | SEX
Como Avaliar a Fiabilidade das Publicações Científicas
Online | Comunidade académica
Inscrição: Membros da UAlg <https://tinyurl.com/4rt2umda>
Externos: cienciaaberta@ualg.pt

PLANNING

CONCLUSION

- **We argue that even the apparent obstacles, such as limited participation in the survey, provide valuable insight into the cultural and structural barriers that must be addressed.**
- **The importance of strengthening communication, training, and support mechanisms for researchers.**
- **By sharing this experience, we hope to contribute to the broader discussion on how to build and maintain institutional capacity for Open Science and accelerate the adoption of FAIR data practices within academia.**

KEY LESSONS FROM OUR OPEN SCIENCE ENGAGEMENT

Low participation is also data. It reflects limited awareness and maybe not lack of interest

Engagement requires visibility. Researchers act when OS seems relevant to their research

Capacity-building matters: Data stewardship and training are the foundation, not an afterthought.

Institutional culture change takes time: building trust and aligning incentives are as vital as policies themselves

Start small, show value: Pilot successes (e.g., Polen Services) inspire broader participation

Short-term actions: finalizing policy, more training sessions, integrating into the national Data Steward network, participation in the Polen Services pilots.

Mid-term goals: first FAIR datasets, improved communication, visible benefits for researchers.

Thank you!